

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF METEKA HYDRATING FACE GEL

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Article Received on 05 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 25 Jan. 2026,
Article Published on 02 Feb. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18479283>

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How to cite this Article: Mariya Thomas*¹, Anisree G. S.¹, Meenu Soman², Akshay K. S.³, Ashika Rahim³, Jerry Boban³, Sara Varghese³. (2026) Formulation And Evaluation of Meteka Hydrating Face Gel World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(2), 815–822.

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ABSTRACT

Face gels are light weight, and hydrating product designed for skin care. Meteka Hydrating face gel is a skincare product designed to provide deep hydration and nourishment to the skin. In present scenario herbal cosmetics have more demand since they have no side effects. In our present study, we attempted four different formulation in gel in different concentrations of form by using Water Hyacinth Extract. Gel formulated by using aloe vera, Carbapol 940, Citric acid, glycerine. The formulations was randomly selected and evaluated with various parameters such as physical appearance, viscosity, pH, spreadability, washability, stability studies. The formulated batch F2 was found excellent effects and selected as the ideal formulation. Also the formulation F2 is having characteristic odour, acceptable color, smooth to touch and spreads efficiently. It absorbs quickly without leaving a greasy residue, offering a refreshing and lightweight feel and is also ideal for all skin types. Regular use of Meteka Hydrating face gel helps to maintain a smooth, hydrated complexion while promoting a healthy, radiant appearance.

KEYWORDS: Meteka Hydrating face gel, Water Hyacinth Extract, Skincare product.

INTRODUCTION

Skin is the largest organ in the body and covers the body's entire external surface. It is made up of three layers epidermis, dermis and the hypodermis.^[1] Face gel.^[2] is a skincare product designed to hydrate, soothe, and refresh the skin. Unlike traditional creams or lotions, face gels have a lightweight, gel-based formula that absorbs quickly into the skin, making them ideal for individuals with oily or combination skin types.^[3] They typically contain water-based ingredients and can include a variety of beneficial components like aloe vera, hyaluronic acid, antioxidants, and botanical extracts. Water hyacinth (*Eichornia crassipes*; Local name: Meteka).^[4] is considered as the most productive plant on earth. Water hyacinth contains antioxidants like flavonoids and polyphenolic compounds that help to protect the skin from free radical damage. The plant is known for its anti-inflammatory properties,^[5] which can help to soothe the irritated or inflamed skin.^[5] Water hyacinth has hydrating properties, making it effective for maintaining skin's moisture balance, it has antibacterial and antifungal activity, which can help in the treatment of fungal infections, and other skin conditions caused by bacteria and fungi. Meteka Hydrating Face Gel is a lightweight, refreshing skincare product designed to deeply hydrate and nourish the skin. This gel formula provides instant moisture while soothing and balancing the skin, leaving it feeling soft, smooth, and revitalized. If it is dry, sensitive, or oily skin, this product absorbs quickly without leaving a greasy residue, making it an ideal addition to skincare routine.^[6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS^[7-9]

A) Materials

The formulation of meteka hydrating face gel was done from the ingredients of natural origin. Meteka (Water Hyacinth) was collected from the herbal garden located locally. The plant was authenticated by Dr.Jacob Thomas, Herbarium curator, Department Of Botany, Mar Thoma college, Thiruvalla. Cosmetic grade Aloe-vera gel, Tea tree oil, Lavender oil were procured from Khadi naturals, Newdelhi .Carbapol940, Citric acid, Triethanolamine were purchased from Isochem Laboratories, Kochi. All other chemicals used for the formulation and evalutaion were of LR grade. Brookfield viscometer, digital balance and other equipments, instruments utilized were also of laboratory grade.

B) Methodology^[10]

Extraction of Water Hyacinth.

Water Hyacinth Extract was done as a result of ethanolic extraction process. Water hyacinth

powder was soaked for 24 hours in the ethanol solution and stored in a dark place to avoid sunlight. After the specified time duration, the obtained extract was then filtered and stored.

Formulation of Face Gel.

Carbopol 940.^[11] was accurately weighed out and then continuously stirred into approximately 50 ml of distilled water. The weighed amount of citric acid was added to distilled water and heated on a water bath to dissolve. Glycerine.^[12] was then poured into the solution once it had cooled. The required amount of water hyacinth extract and aloe vera was added to the above mentioned mixture, and the remaining distilled water was added to bring the volume. Thorough mixing was employed for combining all of the ingredients in the Carbopol 940 gel. Triethanolamine was added drop by drop to the mixture to create the gel's desired consistency as well as to adjust the pH to the desired range. Four different formulations denoted as F1, F2, F3, F4 in gel form were prepared as per the formulation chart described in the Table No: 1. The formulated face gel is presented in Figure No: 1.

Table No: 1 Formulation Chart of Meteka Hydrating Face Gel

INGREDIENTS	BATCH CODE			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
Water Hyacinth (extract)	3 ml	3 ml	3 ml	3 ml
Alovera	1 ml	1ml	1ml	1 ml
Carbapol940	1.3gm	1.2 gm	1.4gm	1.6 gm
Citric acid	0.01 gm	0.01 gm	0.01 gm	0.01 gm
glycerine	6 ml	6 ml	6 ml	6 ml
Triethanolamine	0.8 ml	0.8 ml	0.8 ml	0.8 ml
Tea tree oil	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
Lavender oil	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
DM Water	50 ml	50 ml	50 ml	50 ml

Figure No .1 Formulated Meteka Hydrating Face Gel

EVALUATION OF FACE GEL^[13,18]

The formulated products randomly selected from each batch were evaluated for different parameters to arrive at the ideal formulation. The parameters such as physicochemical evaluation, viscosity, pH, spreadability, washability, were performed. The evaluation parameters include.

1. Colour of the Face Gel

The colour of the face gel was evaluated in black and white and colour backgrounds, The observations were recorded.

2. Odour

Odour is very typical in customer acceptance. The formulations were evaluated and the results were recorded.

3. Spreadability Test^[19]

Spreadability is essentially a measure of how easily the gel can be applied and spread across the skin or a surface. Here the evaluation was done by spreading gently the gel outward from the center of the watch glass. It was spread the gel evenly across the surface in a controlled manner. Measure the distance that the gel spreads or observe the ease with which it moves. A more easily spreadable gel will require less force to spread and will cover a wider area and the results were noted.

4. Homogeneity

The homogeneity of the formulations were evaluated for the smoothness of the formulated facegel.

5. pH^[20]

pH of the formulated samples were evaluated . A 1% solution of the samples were measured by using a digital pH meter at constant temperature. The results were observed and tabulated.

9. Viscosity^[21]

Brookfield viscometer was employed to measure the viscosity. LV-2 spindle was used to measure the viscosity of sample and the readings were recorded.

10. Antimicrobial Activity^[22,25]

Petriplates containing 20ml Muller Hinton Agar Medium were seeded with bacterial culture

of *Staphylococcus aureus*. Wells of approximately 10mm was bored using a well cutter and 100 μ L samples were added. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The antibacterial activity was assayed by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around the well. Streptomycin was used as a positive control. The observations were tabulated in Table No:2 and the observations of microbiological screening presented in Table No:3.

Table No: 2 Evaluation parameter for Meteka Hydrating Face Gel.

Evaluation Parameter	Formulation Identity*			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
Colour	Green	Yellowish Green	Pale yellow	Olive green
Odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour
pH	6.12 \pm 0.05	5.4 \pm 0.11	5.79 \pm 0.09	5.92 \pm 0.14
Spreadability	4.45 \pm 0.08 g-cm/sec	5.5 \pm 0.05g-cm/sec	5 \pm 0.11 g-cm/sec	5.1 \pm 0.06 g-cm/sec
Washability	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable
Homogeneity	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
Viscosity	1467 \pm 0.13mpscI	1458.9 \pm 0.05 mpscI	2000.8 \pm 0.09 mpscI	3009.5 \pm 0.05mpscI

*Average of Three Observations \pm SD

Table No:3 Observations of microbiological study of Meteka Hydrating Face Gel.

Sample	Concentration	Zone of inhibition* (mm)
Water hyacinth face gel	Streptomycin(100 μ g)	27 \pm 0.05
	Water hyacinth face gel(100 μ L)	11 \pm 0.14
ater hyacinth Extract	Water hyacinth Extract (100 μ L)	11 \pm 0.09

*Average of Three Observations \pm SD

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The development and evaluation of face gel was done to fulfill the aim of the research work. The formulation was proceeded by incorporating extract of meteka with aloevera gel, lavender oil, tea tree oil and the gel forming agent carbopol 940. Eichornia crassipes contains a variety of phytoconstituents which contribute several skin benefits. The evaluation of face gel was performed successfully. The development succeeded in the formulation of face gel. Different evaluation parameters were thoroughly analyzed to arrive at an ideal formulation.

From the parameters, all the formulations showed satisfactory visual characteristics, pH, homogeneity, washability, viscosity, and spreadability. All the observations were within the specified range. From that, the batch F2 showed a better intactness to the development. Thus the development will be beneficial for cosmetic lovers. The physicochemical characteristics were identified.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Meteka Hydrating Face Gel is a cosmetic product designed to provide deep hydration and nourishment to the skin. The formulation was done by incorporating Meteka extract with Aloe vera, Tea tree oil. The gel forming agent used was carbopol 940 to get a smooth gel form. The gel promises to restore moisture and smoothens the skin. It is especially beneficial for individuals with dry or sensitive skin, as it helps to lock in moisture without clogging pores. Meteka Hydrating Face Gel is an excellent skincare product for individuals looking to address skin dryness and irritation. With its soothing, lightweight, and deeply hydrating properties, it offers a refreshing alternative to heavier creams, making it suitable for use in both morning and evening routines. Its non-greasy formula ensures that it can be used by all skin types without the risk of breakouts, while its ability to hydrate and smooth the skin makes it a valuable addition to any skincare regimen. The formulation F2 promises its use in dry, oily, or sensitive skin. Also meteka Hydrating Face Gel helps to maintain a well-balanced, refreshed complexion.

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